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Correlational Analysis of Work and Life Satisfaction of Females Working Beyond 8 Hours

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to examine the correlation between the work and life satisfaction of women working beyond eight hours a day in their respective workplaces. Participant sampling came from different working professions in the National Capital Region and Cavite, Philippines, consisting of 50 respondents aged 20 and above. Researchers used criteria-based purposive sampling in selecting the participants to help generate the target respondents for the study. Likert-scale survey questionnaires were utilized to gather the data needed for the study. Moreover, the study used a correlational research design to measure the relationship between life and work satisfaction among the respondents. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA to analyze the level of life satisfaction and work satisfaction when grouped according to the demographic profile of the respondents and the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to better understand the correlation between the said variables. The findings of the study show that there is no significant difference in the levels of life satisfaction and work satisfaction when grouped according to the demographic profile. Moreover, there is a highly significant correlation in terms of the life and work satisfaction of female employees who work beyond eight hours a day.

Keywords: *life satisfaction, work satisfaction, work-life balance, female employees*

Introduction

The degree to which a person assesses the entire worth of his or her life is known as life satisfaction (Ackerman, 2018). In other terms, it refers to how content a person is with their existence. It is a crucial aspect of life that may be evaluated subjectively, where personal opinions on a person's income, wealth, and health problems have an impact on their lives and influence how satisfied they feel with their lives (Uthso & Akter, 2022). On the contrary, job satisfaction relates to how happy employees are doing their jobs. It is a favorable reaction to an employee's experience while carrying out their responsibilities because when people are pleased and content with their occupations, they are more likely to be motivated and productive.

Numerous studies have examined the relationship between feelings of happiness and socioeconomic factors, which include earnings, joblessness, education, and inflation. According to them, the higher the income of each person or the higher the levels of utilization/income, the greater the well-being and happiness of individuals. This is because those with higher incomes can afford to purchase more material goods and services, which can lead to satisfaction, in contrast to those with lower incomes who are not as pleased as those with higher incomes (Dumludag, 2015).

In terms of advancement and equality, women have come a long way, especially in the workplace, where the wage disparity between men and women has narrowed over the past several decades, and women have surpassed men in college enrollment and degrees over the past two decades. Despite having more education and employment opportunities than ever before, women continue to be responsible for the majority of domestic and familial responsibilities. In addition to housework and children, women are substantially more likely to care for ailing or elderly family members. The female labor force participation rate in the Philippines has remained constant at 39 percent for decades, with a slight increase to 39.33% in 2021, except for a slight decline in 2017 and 2018.

Now, the question to be asked is: what is the relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction? This topic has been exhaustively investigated. According to the study by Erdogan (2012), which analyzed a variety of studies on the relationship between life fulfillment and work domain, there is a significant connection between the two. According to a single study, unemployment has a negative impact on life satisfaction and well-being because having a job is a source of need satisfaction, especially for financial requirements. Repeated unemployment negatively impacts life satisfaction, whereas secured employment has a positive impact.

This study investigates if there is a link between the levels of life and work satisfaction of women who work more than eight hours per day to determine whether the levels of work satisfaction influence the level of life satisfaction of women employees. This information can assist organizations and female employees in understanding how to maintain work satisfaction while also maintaining life fulfillment when working longer than eight hours per day.

Research Questions

This study intended to establish a correlational study on the levels of life and work satisfaction of women working beyond eight hours in the Philippines. Specifically, this research intends to answer the succeeding queries:

1. What is the demographic profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;

- 1.2. Marital Status;
- 1.3. Place of Residence;
- 1.4. Working Profession;
2. What is the level of life satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile?
3. What is the level of work satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of work satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of life satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile?
6. Is there a significant correlation between work and life satisfaction?

Methodology

Research Design

Since the purpose of this study is to ascertain the correlation between the levels of life satisfaction and work satisfaction among women employees that are working more than 8 hours every week in their respective workplaces, the researchers employed a correlational research design. It is the most suitable research design for the topic because it is used to measure two or more variables to assess the degree to which the values of the factors being studied are related.

Respondents

The samples for the study were gathered using criterion purposeful sampling, wherein the criteria set by the researchers are only focused on women who are currently working beyond eight hours on a day-to-day basis. The participants of the study were selected based on a particular profile – women between the ages of 20 and above currently working beyond normal working hours. The researchers were able to gather a total of 50 participants to answer the Google Form and their demographic profiles can be seen in the table below. They were arranged based on their age, marital status, place of residence, and working profession, wherein the researchers used the International Standard Classification of Occupations 2008 as their basis for categorizing the different jobs of the respondents. Majority of the respondents are working as Administrative and Commercial Managers, Self-Employed – this includes freelancers and business owners – and Sales and Marketing Managers.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

Profile	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	30 and Below	35	70.0
	31-40 Years Old	11	22.0
	41 and Above	4	8.0
Marital Status	Single	38	76.0
	Married	9	18.0
	Separated	2	4.0
	Widowed	1	2.0
Place of Residence	Cavite	30	60.0
	NCR	20	40.0
Working Profession (Based on ISCO-08)	Legal Professionals	1	2.00
	Self-Employed	6	12.00
	Advertising and Marketing Professionals	1	2.00
	Data Entry Clerks	3	6.00
	Sales and Marketing Managers	5	10.00
	Database and Network Professionals	1	2.00
	Administrative and Commercial Managers	11	22.00
	Personal Services Workers	3	6.00
	Client Information Workers	2	4.00
	Sales Workers	2	4.00
	Engineering Professionals	1	2.00
	Authors and Related Writers	1	2.00
	Sports and Fitness Workers	1	2.00
	Teaching Professionals	2	4.00
	Clerical Support Workers	4	8.00
	Health Professionals	1	2.00
Customer Services Clerks	2	4.00	
Human Resource Managers	3	6.00	

Instrument

In gathering the data that is relevant to the study, researchers utilized the Likert Scale to create a set of close-ended questions as their survey instrument to elicit fitting information from the selected participants of the study. The questionnaire was created into three parts, the first part contains the profile information of the respondent, including their age, marital status, place of residence, and working profession, while the second part of the questionnaire contains 15 close-ended questions in the form of a Likert-scale about life satisfaction and the third section of the Google Form contained another 15 questions that would help in measuring the work satisfaction of women working beyond 8 hours that are needed in order to analyze the correlation between life satisfaction and work satisfaction

of the target respondents.

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Indicators	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
Life Satisfaction	0.931	15
Work Satisfaction	0.928	15
Whole Output	0.956	30

In addition, the researchers used Cronbach's alpha to calculate the internal reliability or consistency of the instruments utilized during the study to determine if the items considered by the researchers measured the same characteristics consistently. The items for Life Satisfaction garnered Cronbach's alpha value of 0.931, which according to the level of reliability is considered to be 'Excellent or Very Reliable,' and the score for Work Satisfaction is 0.928, which has the same reliability rating. Therefore, the aggregate result is deemed 'Excellent or Very Reliable,' signifying that the instrument developed by the researchers for the study passed the reliability test.

Procedure

The researchers of the study first secured the consent of the participants through an informed consent section in the google survey. Once the consent of the participants is secured, the researchers then brief the respondents of the research about the focus of the study and its purpose. Aside from briefing the participants, the researchers also used a Likert Scale set of questions answered by the participants using Google Forms Survey. Furthermore, the researchers ensure the safety of the data gathered from the respondents and its confidentiality.

Data Analysis

The researchers employed statistics to evaluate the responses collected from participants. This includes the percentage to determine the personal variables of the participants, such as their age, place of residence, and occupation, the weighted means to determine the evaluation of the respondents, and the frequency distribution to sum up the total number of responses to each question. For the statistical analysis of the data collected to determine the difference between the levels of life satisfaction and work satisfaction, the researchers used analysis of variance, and for the correlation of work and life satisfaction for women working more than eight hours, Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was used, allowing them to determine if there is a relationship between working more than eight hours and the degree of life and work satisfaction.

Results and Discussion

Characteristics of Data

This section foothold the characteristics of data analysis for each value to their average frequency count that fit the data samples 50, and the following tables shows the different level of life and work satisfaction, including weights of data parameters followed by the interpretation of inferential statistics output.

Table 3. Mean Response on the Level of Life Satisfaction

Life Satisfaction	1	2	3	4	5	AWM	SD	VI
1. I have enough time for my family and friends.	0	6	20	14	10	3.56	0.951	Often
2. I spend quality time with my friends and family	1	11	17	12	9	3.34	1.081	Sometimes
3. I can still manage responsibilities at home	0	10	9	21	10	3.62	1.028	Often
4. I am able to manage personal errands	1	4	18	16	11	3.64	0.985	Often
5. I can give proper attention to my life	1	6	13	18	12	3.68	1.039	Often
6. I am not able to miss personal activities	0	12	19	12	7	3.28	0.991	Sometimes
7. I am happy with life	0	5	14	18	13	3.78	0.954	Often
8. I am able to do things at home that makes me happy	0	7	15	14	14	3.70	1.035	Often
9. My work helps me achieve my goals in life.	1	6	10	14	19	3.88	1.118	Often
10. I can still make time for my hobbies.	4	12	14	10	10	3.20	1.245	Sometimes
11. I am able to have personal vacations	6	9	12	12	11	3.26	1.322	Sometimes
12. I have a sense of satisfaction in life	0	8	16	12	14	3.64	1.064	Often
13. Life demands are manageable	1	9	23	11	6	3.24	0.960	Sometimes
14. I can find time to do self-care activities	2	10	15	11	12	3.42	1.180	Often
15. I am comfortable with what life I have now.	1	8	16	13	12	3.54	1.092	Often
Overall Mean Value						3.52	1.070	Often

Legend: (1.00 – 1.80): Never, (1.81 – 2.60): Rarely, (2.61 – 3.40): Sometimes, (3.41 – 4.20): Often, (4.21 – 5.00): Always, AWM – Average Weighted Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

The mean of the responses used to determine the level of life satisfaction of the respondents is displayed in the table above. From 1 to 15, the majority of the average weighted mean of responses for each item lies within the 'Often' range. Consequently, the aggregate mean value of the participants' responses to the Level of Life Satisfaction falls within the 'Often' range, indicating that women working more than 8 hours per week are frequently content with their lives.

Table 4. Mean Response on the Level of Work Satisfaction

Work Satisfaction	1	2	3	4	5	AWM	SD	VI
1. I am working with a supportive work environment	1	6	18	11	14	3.62	1.086	Often
2. I can balance the priorities at work	1	4	19	14	12	3.64	1.005	Often
3. I am satisfied with my work	2	8	12	14	14	3.60	1.178	Often
4. I am happy with the benefits that I get from my work	1	12	14	12	11	3.40	1.143	Sometimes
5. I am able to manage work errands	0	6	19	14	11	3.60	0.969	Often
6. The demand at work helps me to become a better employee	0	7	14	15	14	3.72	1.031	Often
7. I am able to finish tasks at the office	1	2	14	19	14	3.86	0.948	Often
8. I feel happy at work	1	9	12	21	7	3.48	1.015	Often
9. I am incentivized properly with my work	3	8	12	16	11	3.48	1.182	Often
10. Pressure in the workplace is manageable	0	9	19	14	8	3.42	0.971	Often
11. My jobs helps me to be professionally happy	1	8	16	10	15	3.60	1.143	Often
12. I feel happy when I am working intensely.	4	5	20	13	8	3.32	1.115	Sometimes
13. I don't have negative emotions at work	2	12	24	9	3	2.98	0.915	Sometimes
14. My job helps me to become a better person	1	3	12	21	13	3.84	0.955	Often
15. Performing many roles simultaneously is fine with me	2	6	16	16	10	3.52	1.074	Often
Overall Mean Value						3.54	1.049	Often

Legend: (1.00 – 1.80): Never, (1.81 – 2.60): Rarely, (2.61 – 3.40): Sometimes, (3.41 – 4.20): Often, (4.21 – 5.00): Always. AWM – Average Weighted Mean. SD – Standard Deviation. VI – Verbal Interpretation

A similar computation from Table 3 was used to determine the mean of responses to also assess the Level of Work Satisfaction of women working beyond 8 hours. According to the table above, the overall mean value of the responses is 3.54, which means that women working over normal working hours often feel satisfied with their work.

Inferential Statistics

This sector contains the significant part that was obtained in statistical analysis foothold of the characteristics of each demographic variable, including the level of work satisfaction and level of life satisfaction.

Table 5. Difference on the Level of Work Satisfaction When Grouped According to Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Work Satisfaction		Decision	Interpretation
	f	sig.		
Age	0.588 ^{ns}	0.85	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Marital Status	0.441 ^{ns}	0.72	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Place of Residence	0.276 ^{ns}	0.60	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Working Profession	1.643 ^{ns}	0.16	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: ns - Not Significant at 5% level of significance.

The table above displays the statistical analysis of the significant difference in the Level of work satisfaction based on the respondents' demographic characteristics. All of the variables in the demographic profile have significant values greater than 0.05. If the significance value is greater than the level of significance, which is 5%, then there is no significant difference, and the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 6. *Difference on the Level of Life Satisfaction When Grouped According to Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

Profile	Life Satisfaction		Decision	Interpretation
	<i>f</i>	sig.		
Age	0.868-	0.597	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Marital Status	1.006-	0.399	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Place of Residence	0.259-	0.613	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Working Profession	0.541-	0.744	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Note: ns - Not Significant at 5% level of significance.

The preceding table depicts the statistical analysis of the significant difference in the level of life satisfaction when respondents are classified according to their demographic profile. All variables in the demographic profile have significant values greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference in the level of life satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to their demographic profile.

Table 7. *Correlation Between the Level of Life Satisfaction and Level of Work Satisfaction*

Indicators	Life Satisfaction		Decision	Interpretation
	<i>f</i>	p-value (sig.)		
Work Satisfaction	0.757**	0.000	Reject Ho	Significantly High

Note: ** - Significantly High at 5% alpha level (2-tailed).

The correlation test between the level of life satisfaction and the level of work satisfaction for women working over 8 hours is displayed in the table above. The result indicates a positive correlation between the Level of Life Satisfaction and Work Satisfaction because the p-value obtained is less than the 0.05 alpha level, indicating that the level of life satisfaction and work satisfaction is significantly high, correlated, and important.

Demographic Profile

Respondents of all ages – from 20 to over 40 – were represented, with a large difference in number in the lowest age bracket, which is 30 years old and below, accounting for 35 (70%) of the respondents compared to respondents from the ages 31 to 40 and ages 41 and above accounting for 11 (22%) and 4 (8%) of the respondents. The wide difference between the younger age bracket compared to the 31 to 41 and above age group can be attributed to the employment situation of the Philippines presented by the Philippine Statistics Authority in 2018, wherein the largest number of employed persons consists of Filipinos from the 25 to 34 years old age group with a total of 26.9%, while the second largest group are comprised with the 35 years old to 44 years old age group and the third largest group are from the age bracket of 45 to 54 years of age (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2019). Moreover, the majority of the respondents (76%) are ‘Single’ based on their answers when asked about their marital status, which is in contradiction with (Gammarano, 2020) wherein the author stated in the article that single people have a greater possibility to be jobless than married people, as the unemployment rate among prime-age single men and women is higher than that of married individuals, according to data compiled by the International Labour Organization from 103 countries. According to (Apostolou et al., 2020), many single people are in Western countries. This is supported by data from (Todd, 2021), which indicates that singles make up a significant portion of the population of adults in the United States, similar to England and Wales, where 35% of the population has never been married. Singlehood has been growing in Asia too, where 43% of South Koreans in their 30’s is unmarried, while the population of single Japanese women between the age of 18 and 39 increased from 27% in 1992 to 41% in the year 2015. A survey from Pew Research Center in 2020 found that one of the reasons why people weren’t looking to date or be in a relationship is because they were prioritizing other parts of their lives at present, such as working on their careers. In terms of the place of residence, 30 (60%) of the respondents came from different cities in Cavite, while 20 (40%) of the respondents were from the National Capital Region. The reason behind this might be due to the fact that 4 out of 6 of the researchers are from Cavite. Hence it is more likely that the survey was relayed within their cities compared to the 2 researchers that live in NCR.

Lastly, women working in the field of administrative and commercial managers, sales and marketing managers, and women that are self-employed have the highest frequency in the result of the study. Other working professions such as sales workers, the teaching profession, human resource managers, and data entry clerks are also some of the jobs that the respondents of the study have. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, occupation groups such as professionals, clerks, officials of the government and special interest organizations, corporate executives, managers, managing proprietors, supervisory jobs, service workers, and show and market sales

are those that are dominated by women while the rest of the occupation groups are highly dominated by men. Aside from that, Sarawagi (2022) stated that there is an increase of women freelancers in India nowadays which caused a large growth in numbers in the freelancing economy. One of the reasons was that women have more power now to define the path that they want to take in their careers, which causes the rise of participation of women in the workforce. Aside from that, females from India are becoming more interested in freelancing because of its advantages, such as having the independence to work at your own pace, choices with a larger income, and can help women to develop their skills more. On their website, the International Labor Organization gave a list of jobs that are dominated by women based on the available data for 121 countries. Occupations such as personal care workers, health associate professionals, teaching professionals, customer services clerks, clerical support workers, legal, social, and cultural professionals, business and administration professionals, and sales workers are some of the jobs that are mostly filled by women, which can explain why Category 4 and 6 has the largest number of responses compared to other job categories.

Level of Life Satisfaction

Based on the overall mean value for the level of life satisfaction of women working beyond 8 hours, they are often satisfied with their life. Most of the respondents stated that they still have enough time to bond with their family and friends, and they can still manage their responsibilities at home while giving proper attention to their life. Some stated that they can still make time for their hobbies and to enjoy personal vacations even though they are working beyond the normal working hours. Work-life balance, which refers to an individual's ability to create a balanced schedule for their professional and personal hours to live a healthy and happy life, can be a factor for the satisfaction of women working beyond 8 hours since it focuses on developing women's values and attitudes towards arranging and balancing their work and personal lives (Bhat, 2021). However, work-life balance is not something that can be attained immediately. It needs effort from the employee, the employee's family, the organization where the employee works, and the society or community in which the employee lives. Women typically work full-time, working a minimum of 8 hours per day, five days per week, with increasing responsibilities daily. As a result, most of them have both work and family responsibilities, especially women that are married and with children, although women that are single also have unpaid work activities such as household work and caregiving for both the elderly and children in their household. Managing work and family together can be challenging for women, especially for working mothers, and can cause their quality of life to be hampered. That is why work-life balance is important. Bhat (2021) suggested that to avoid work-family conflict, family relationships, and workplace disputes, every woman needs to establish a goal to succeed in both her work and her family. Planning, organizing, and setting limits are some of the approaches and abilities utilized at home and work to achieve a comfortable and gratifying harmonious lifestyle both professionally and personally.

Additionally, it is valuable to consider the marital status of those who participated. A large number of respondents are unmarried, which may explain why they are satisfied with their lives despite working more than 8 hours per week. According to Paul Dolan (2023), instructor of behavioral science at the London School of Economics, childless women are the happiest. In addition, (Bien et al., 2017) found that women who choose not to have children have a better quality of life and a healthier view of their own well-being.

According to the findings of the investigation of the difference in the level of life satisfaction of women based on their demographic profile (Table 6), there is no significant difference in the level of life satisfaction, opposite to what previous researchers have claimed, which is that several factors, such as health, employment, and education, can influence the development of an individual's life satisfaction, as described by Lahamuddin (2013). A possible explanation for why the hypothesized result was not observed is that the sample size was small and restricted to a particular group of individuals, namely women who work beyond normal working hours. Researchers were only able to recruit 50 participants due to time constraints, which may have affected the results. Future research on the life and job contentment of women must take this into consideration. These demographic factors were not analyzed by the researchers, which may have led to the rejection of the alternative hypothesis and should be considered by future researchers conducting a similar study.

Level of Work Satisfaction

According to Table 4, women working beyond 8 hours often feel satisfied with their work. Some answered that they have a supportive working environment, they are incentivized properly, and the pressure in their workplace is manageable, which leads to their frequent satisfaction at their work. Hill (2019) outlined in his article multiple factors that affect an employee's job satisfaction, such as having a pleasant working environment because employees spend so much time at work, and it is important that organizations try to improve the employees' working environment, for instance, by providing tools for productivity that can help workers to complete more tasks efficiently, which may contribute to the employee's job satisfaction. Another article entitled "Factors influencing Job Satisfaction" stated that organizational factors like salaries and wages can play a significant role in influencing job satisfaction. Simply stated, money is an indispensable resource for meeting one's needs. Second, employees frequently associate money with management's concern for them. Lastly, a higher salary is viewed as a symbol of success because it indicates greater devotion to organizational operations. In addition, a healthy working environment that can provide support, comfort, and assistance to the individual members of the group can influence job satisfaction, and if people are difficult to get along with, the workgroup is more likely to have a negative effect on Job Satisfaction.

The data suggests that there is not a statistically significant difference in Work Satisfaction among respondents when they are classified based on their demographic characteristics. In the study conducted by Shrestha (2019), the impact of eight demographic factors, namely

designation, age, gender, service year, education, income, service type, and type of higher education, on job satisfaction parameters, including social recognition, working environment, compensation, promotion, recognition, and union were examined. The study conducted by the author revealed that out of the eight variables, monthly income and designation exhibited a higher degree of significance compared to the remaining variables. The aforementioned assertion is corroborated by Islam's (2019) study, wherein the researchers conducted an analysis of the effects of demographic variables on job satisfaction. The study revealed that job satisfaction remains unaffected by sexual orientation, marital status, and position, while age and experience exert a significant influence.

Correlation Between the Level of Life Satisfaction and Level of Work Satisfaction

The findings of the correlational analysis conducted on the relationship between the levels of life satisfaction and work satisfaction indicate a positive correlation. This is supported by the obtained p-value, which is below the alpha level of .05, indicating a highly significant correlation between work and life satisfaction among women who work beyond 8 hours. The study conducted by Unanue et al. (2017) explored the correlation between life satisfaction and work satisfaction and revealed a significant association between the two variables and numerous favorable outcomes in both personal and professional domains. Additionally, Diener and Tay (2012) have established a positive relationship between life satisfaction and higher levels of career satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction. Therefore, it is imperative for organizations to consider various factors that impact the job satisfaction of their employees, as it can also have an impact on their overall life satisfaction.

All things considered, it is known that the relationship between work satisfaction and life satisfaction for women working beyond 8 hours is positive. As stated in the study of Yazicioglu (2017), the higher the individual's income is, the higher the life satisfaction that individual feels. The result of the study can offer a new insight when it comes to the relationship between life and work satisfaction as it focuses more on the analysis of women working beyond 8 hours and how it was identified that even though they are working outside of normal working hours, they are satisfied with their life at work and their personal life. However, it is only conducted within Cavite and the National Capital Region. It would be an interesting study if it could also be conducted in the different rural and urban areas in the Philippines.

Conclusions

Based on the gathered data, the researchers concluded that 70% of the respondents were 30 years old and below. The marital status of the respondents shows that 76.0% were identified as single. And the majority of the place of residency of the respondents came from Cavite, which is 60.0%. The highest responses came from the Administrative and Commercial Managers, which is 22.0%

This research explored the influence of demographic factors on the level of life satisfaction of women working beyond 8 hours and found that demographic factors such as Age, Marital Status, Working Profession, and place of residence don't have a significant difference in the level of life satisfaction among the participants.

Researchers found that women from different professions working beyond 8 hours are frequently satisfied with their work and personal life. However, this could be due to the fact that the majority of the respondents are single.

The relationship between life satisfaction and work satisfaction of women is highly correlated with each other. Therefore, as work satisfaction increases, life satisfaction also increases.

The following recommendations are presented:

Future psychology researchers

They may examine other demographic variables such as their income and education and if there is a significant difference in the level of life and work satisfaction of women if additional demographic factors are added.

They may also consider collecting a wider range of data to be able to provide more detailed information about the life and work satisfaction of women working beyond 8 hours. Aside from that, it is also recommended to focus on a single working profession, level of position, and age group to be able to identify whether women in that field of work are satisfied with their profession and life.

Lastly, they can also consider conducting the study in different urban and rural areas in the Philippines to see if the place of residence influences the life and work satisfaction of women.

Community:

The researchers may suggest having more understanding of the situations of women in the workplace, especially those who work beyond eight hours, to have an in-depth understanding of the factors and reasons for doing so. It is necessary for the community to build a more positive environment that will benefit not just the female employees but also the people in the community.

Mental Health Practitioner:

They may examine the different factors that push women to work beyond 8 hours and the possible stressors that working women experience that can affect their life satisfaction and work satisfaction.

Employee

They may practice a healthy work-life balance to enhance their capabilities of being satisfied in their life and work and actively participate in the activities and programs that are necessary for fostering the life and work satisfaction of the employees to increase their success in their respective workplaces.

St. Dominic College of Asia

The researchers may recommend with great pleasure the institution provide a more systematic approach to organizing programs that will be implemented by the employees to foster the skills in preparing them to be more competitive in their respective workplaces without enduring their life and work satisfaction.

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